

**Report
on
Seed Diversity, Germination, Plant Standing and Harvesting**

**PART- 2
RABI SEASON**

**State Name: West Bengal
Third Reintroduction of Farmer's Varieties
2022-2023**

Fig.: Yellow Mustard Germination and after harvesting; Passbook Number 735206-01-0132

**Submitted To
FAO, ITPGRFA IV CYCLE PROJECT**

**By
Vikas Arora
Project Coordinator
PAIRVI
New Delhi**

Under the project

Improving pulse biodiversity in rice fallow areas of tribal belts of Central and East Indian states to bring resilience in the farming practice, provide livelihood support and enhance nutritional level of the tribal population.

RABI SEASON

Seed Biodiversity Report

Time Period for Sowing: November 2022

Mustard, (Black)	Local haat - Haldibari
Mustard, (Yellow)	Improved variety
Mustard, (Yellow)	Farmer variety – Dilip Roy

Seed Distributed:

Yellow Mustard distribution to Anita Das(left) and Yellow Mustard distribution to Ramen Roy.

Black Mustard distribution to Prashanto Das

Black Mustard distribution to Esraful Islam

Yellow Mustard Distribution to Bhaleswari Roy and Yellow Mustard sowing in field of Ram Munda

Black gram seed collection from farmer Dipak Roy (left) and farmers field visit by official from agriculture department for seeds treatment demonstration.

Germination report:

Crop: Black Mustard, Yellow Mustard

Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 735206-01-0132, 30, 89)

Passbook No.	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing date	Date of Germination 50%	Any pest attack	Water logging	Other vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestions
735206-01-0132	Mustard (black)	Local haat - Haldibari	07/12/2022	18/12/2022	No	No	No	Land preparation
735206-01-0130	Mustard (yellow)	Improved variety	09/12/2022	18/12/2022	No	No	No	
735206-01-0089	Mustard (yellow)	Farmer variety – Dilip Roy	03/12/2022	13/12/2022	No	No	No	

Yellow Mustard Germination field of Ramen Roy.

Yellow Mustard Germination field of Raghunath Munda.

Irrigation of Yellow Mustard Field of Raghunath Munda.

Mustard germination in the field of Tez Bahadur Sonar

Field Activities in Field during the period germination and standing of plant:

Dated	Activities	Outcomes
01/12/22	Training on participatory plant variety selections.	Project farmers have knowledge on how to select the different plants variety.
02/12/22	Result sharing stakeholder's workshops.	Shared the project activities and results among different stakeholders and agriculture department agreed to support the project farmers.
09/12/22	Farmers field visit.	Yellow mustard distribution Anita Das.
10/12/22	Field visit	Yellow mustard distribution and sowing in the field of farmer, Ramen Roy
12/12/22	Field visit	Yellow mustard distribution and sowing in the field of farmer, Raghunath Munda
15/12/22	Field visit	Black mustard distribution to the farmer, Prashanto Das
18/12/22	Field visit	Good germination of yellow mustard in the field of farmer, field Ramen Roy
19/12/22	Field visit	Black mustard distribution to the farmer, Esraful Islam
20/12/22	Field visit	Yellow mustard germination at satisfactory level in the of field Raghunath Munda
22/12/22	Field visit	Yellow mustard distribution to the farmer, Bhaleswari Roy
24/12/22	Field visit	Good germination of yellow mustard in the field of farmer, Ram Munda.
29/12/22	Field visit	Irrigation in the mustard field of Raghunath Munda after suggestion from the project

Pod and Harvesting report:

Crop: Black Mustard, Chana, Masoor

Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 0010, 004, 0012,0017,0021)

Trial Plot No./Passbook no.	Crop Name variety name	Pod appearing date/	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plant	Any disease observed in plants so far	Harvesting of pods date	Quantity (kg)of seed got from trial plot	Color of Pod and No of Seed in pod	Other Vulnerable Factor
735206-01-0089	Haldibari haat variety	18/02/23	23	48	No	22/03/23	70 kg	Yellow	No
735206-01-0130	Improved variety (B9)	21/02/23	24	51	No	27/03/23	98 kg	Yellow	No
735206-01-0132	Farmer variety (Dilip Roy)	24/02/23	22	46	No	25/03/23	66 kg	Yellow	No

Scientist Present there: Yes

Note:

1. Sequence of Trial plot No. for Best Growth:

Best growth735206-01-0130; **Less growth** 735206-01-132

2. Trial Farm with SAME/EQUAL farmers' varieties:

Identified Characteristics

Mustard	(seed size, seed color, Plant size and color, Branches, Hairy stem or leaves and others, Flowering time)
1. Haldibari haat variety	Yellow colour, round shap, smaller size and plant height 33 inch
2. Improved variety (B9)	Yellow colour, round and bigger size, plant height 38 inch
3. Farmer variety (Dilip Roy)	Yellow colour, round shap, smaller size and plant height 33 inch

735206-01-0089

735206-01-0132

735206-01-0130
